

MATHEMATICS “CONTENT KNOWLEDGE” AND “PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE”

Dr. Ritu Bala⁸

Abstract

Teachers’ knowledge is a key factor to students’ achievement. One could question what this teachers’ knowledge comprises of content knowledge or pedagogical content knowledge or both. Whether acquiring Mathematics content knowledge alone adequately prepares prospective Mathematics teachers for teaching mathematics. Specifically, does the mastery in arithmetic, algebra, geometry, trigonometry, calculus etc. prepare future teachers to be highly competent to teach students or just acquiring pedagogical knowledge alone adequately prepares prospective Mathematics teachers for teaching mathematic. In the 1980’s, Lee Shulman and his colleagues coined a new term “pedagogical content knowledge” to answer these questions and categorized teacher’s knowledge in seven categories and this give a start to the new debate which one is more better content knowledge or pedagogical content knowledge. This paper is an attempt to define and elaborate the difference and relationship between these two terms Mathematics content knowledge or Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge to make them more understandable to the Mathematics teachers.

Teachers’ knowledge is a key factor to students’ academic success in today’s classrooms. There have been many debates on the underlying interpretation of what Mathematics teacher’s knowledge includes Mathematics content knowledge or Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge or both. What is the difference or relation between these two?

⁸ Dr. Ritu Bala, Email: ritu_bala11@yahoo.com

In the 1980's, Lee Shulman and his colleagues popularized the concept of "pedagogical content knowledge" and introduced a new way of thinking about the nature and role of the teacher's knowledge needed for high academic success of students Shulman (1986). In 1987, Shulman distinguished teacher's knowledge in seven categories: content knowledge; curricular knowledge; pedagogical content knowledge; general pedagogical knowledge; knowledge of learners and their characteristics; knowledge of educational contexts and knowledge of educational ends, purposes and values. Ever since Shulman established these categories, many researchers have come to believe that pedagogical content knowledge is an important topic in Mathematics education and that high levels of pedagogical content knowledge will predict high levels of student achievement and this believe has further grounded the platform for discussion to which one is most important content knowledge or pedagogical content knowledge.

Figure1

Shulman's Seven Categories of Teacher's Knowledge

Ball's studies (1990) showed that effective Mathematics teaching is linked to both teachers' subject matter content knowledge as well as their pedagogical content knowledge. Heid et al. (1999) showed that secondary Mathematics' teachers content knowledge influences their instructional planning and classroom practice. Heather et al. (2005) found that teachers' mathematical knowledge was significantly related to student achievement. Waller (2012) found positive relationship of Mathematics intervention teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and students' math achievement gains in primary math interventions.

The above-mentioned studies show a significant relation between Mathematics content knowledge, Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge, effective Mathematics teaching and students' math achievement. Before reaching to any conclusion, one must have a deeper insight to both of these terms Mathematics content knowledge, Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge. Mathematics content knowledge is common knowledge of mathematical content. It is the subject matter knowledge and refers to general Mathematics ability. It includes knowledge about axioms, postulates, theorems, rules, principles, formulae, language, concepts, sub-concepts etc. of Mathematics, depth, breadth, accuracy and application of content knowledge; connections within and between topics and the branches of Mathematics and fluency with multiple modes of examples of a topic and getting solution to a particular mathematical problems. On the other hand, Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge is defined as the specialized content knowledge required for teaching Mathematics. It includes, "the most useful forms of representation ..., the most powerful analogies, illustrations, examples, explanations, and demonstrations - in a word, the most useful ways of representing and formulating the subject that make it comprehensible to others.... Pedagogical content knowledge also includes an understanding of what makes the learning of specific topics easy or difficult" (Shulman, 1986).

Pedagogical content knowledge is the knowledge of how to transform formal content knowledge into meaningful learning outcomes for students and it involves an understanding of a particular topic and the ways a teacher explains the topic or concepts to make sense to the students in the classroom. Teachers are always expected to exhibit a basic set of pedagogical knowledge and skills in the classroom, which involves a good knowledge of Mathematics, teaching methods, skills and knowledge of child development etc. This is emphasized by (Hill et al 2004) that "In performing the process of teaching and learning,

teachers bring along with them the knowledge components, content knowledge, good knowledge about the students and the various ways of using content knowledge in a classroom's teaching and learning process indeed play a role". Moreover, the integration of all these knowledge is recognized as pedagogical content knowledge.

For an example, teachers of Mathematics need a special type of understanding of mathematical content itself. "A powerful characteristic of Mathematics is its capacity to compress information into abstract and highly usable forms. . . . Mathematicians rely on this compression in their work. However, teachers work with Mathematics as it is being learned, which requires a kind of decompression, or 'unpacking' of ideas" (Ball and Bass, 2003). This "unpacked" knowledge may provide the foundation for knowing how to represent the subject to students or how to understand the mathematical features of student work. Most adults, for example, know that one can "invert and multiply" to get the correct answer to the problem: $\frac{3}{4}$ divided by $\frac{1}{2}$. However, Mathematics teachers must know why such rules work and how to represent the Mathematics to facilitate student understanding. Is a student mathematically correct in saying that this problem can be illustrated by splitting $\frac{3}{4}$ pies evenly between two families or in saying that this can be illustrated by calculating how much money you would have if you doubled Rs.0.75? If not correct, then what is a good story problem that illustrates $\frac{3}{4}$ divided by $\frac{1}{2}$? Good Mathematics teachers know how to address such questions and how to unpack and represent fractions in ways that are useful in teaching the subject.

Pedagogical content knowledge includes "...understanding of how particular topics, problems, or issues are organized, presented, and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners" and the "...most useful forms of representation of these ideas, most powerful analogies, illustrations, examples, explanations, and demonstrations" and "...the ways of representing and formulating the subject that make it comprehensible to others" (Shulman, 1987). The relation and difference between the Mathematics content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge can be better understood from the following table:

Table: Mathematics content knowledge vs. Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge

Dimensions of Knowledge	Mathematics Content Knowledge	Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge
<i>Field of Knowledge</i>	Mathematics	Mathematics Education
<i>Output of Knowledge</i>	Enables to be skilled and competent Mathematics student/s	Enables to be skilled and competent Mathematics teacher/s
<i>Knowledge is Mastered by</i>	The learner/student	The teacher
<i>Objective of Getting Knowledge</i>	To master the rules, principles, formulae etc. of Mathematics to solve the problems based on them	To transform mathematical knowledge into meaningful learning outcomes for students to make them understand the rules, principles, formulae etc. of Mathematics
<i>Basic Requirements for Knowledge</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The will to learn Mathematics • Attitude towards learning Mathematics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The will to teach Mathematics • Aptitude for teaching Mathematics
<i>Areas of Study of Knowledge</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concepts and sub-concepts of Mathematics • The relation within and between the branches of Mathematics • Solution of Mathematical problems related to the concepts of arithmetic, algebra, geometry, statistics, trigonometry etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching of Mathematics • The content knowledge • Content analysis • Pedagogical analysis • Psychology of teaching and learning • Learner and her/his characteristics • Methods of evaluation etc.
<i>Knowledge is Mastered Through</i>	Drill work techniques and practice while learning	Training and practice during teaching
<i>Basis for</i>	Pure Mathematics and Sciences	Behavioural Sciences

<i>Knowledge</i>		
<i>Relation</i>	Without pedagogical content knowledge a teacher will not be teach effectively in the class. less effective teaching results in less effective content knowledge	Without mastery of content knowledge, teacher cannot master the pedagogical content knowledge.

From the above table it is clear that there is difference between to master the concept her/himself and to make others master the content. The first one refers to the content knowledge and the second one refers to the pedagogical content knowledge. To make students master the Mathematics content knowledge the teacher her/himself has to master the Mathematics content knowledge along with Mathematics pedagogical knowledge and contextual knowledge. Mathematics pedagogical knowledge is “the knowledge or the study of science of teaching mathematical concepts and sub-concepts that influences the Mathematics learning in students”. Therefore we can conclude that Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge includes three sub-components: Mathematics content knowledge – Knowledge of the contents of Mathematics, pedagogical knowledge - knowledge of science of teaching, content analysis, pedagogical analysis, methods and techniques of presentation and contextual knowledge - the level, characteristics and needs of the students as well as the subject, teaching-learning environment.

Figure 2

Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge

A teacher with good mathematical pedagogical content knowledge can break down mathematical content knowledge into less polished and abstract forms, thus making it accessible to students who are at different cognitive levels. S/he can unpack the Mathematics into its discrete elements and can explain a concept or procedure at a level that includes the steps necessary for the students to make sense of the reasoning. S/he can understand where students may have trouble learning the subject and will be able to represent mathematical concepts in a way that their students can comprehend its structure and avoid these difficulties. In order to prepare effective Mathematics teachers, a teacher-training program must focus on Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge.

References:

- Ball, D. L. (1990). The mathematical understandings that prospective teachers bring to teacher education, *Elementary School Journal*, 90(4).
- Ball, D. L. and Bass, H. (2003). Toward a practice-based theory of mathematical knowledge for teaching. In Phelps, G. and Schilling, S. (2004). *Developing measures of content knowledge for teaching reading*, Elementary School Journal. Online sii.soe.umich.edu/.../ESJ_CKT%20reading_Final_Reformatted.pdf
- Heather C. Hill, Brian Rowan, and Deborah Loewenberg Ball (2005) Effects of Teachers' Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching on Student Achievement American, *Educational Research Journal*, 42(2).

- Heid, M. K., Blume, G. W., Zbiek, R. M., & Edwards, B. S. (1999). Factors that influence teachers learning to do interviews to understand students' mathematical understandings, *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 37.
- Hill, H.C., Ball, D. L. & Schilling, S. G. (2004). Developing measures of teachers' mathematics knowledge for teaching, *Elementary School Journal*, 105.
- Shulman, L. S. (1986). Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching, *Educational Researcher*, 15(2).
- Shulman, L. S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1).
- Waller, Lisa Ivey (2012) *Math intervention teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and student achievement*, Eastern Kentucky University Richmond, Kentucky. Online <http://encompass.eku.edu/etd/57>.
